

THE PROCEDURE FOR THE EVALUATION OF INNOVATION PROJECTS IN ENTERPRISES AND SELECTION METHODS

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Annotation. In this article, the evaluation of innovation projects in the enterprise, analysis, and review of thinking about their selection, concepts and causing the tips mentioned.

Keywords: directory, market, innovation, IC(innovative enterprises)

To enter. Today's the competitiveness of economic entities in the conditions of market relations plays an important role. In this technical and economic entities technology improvements, new technologies to meet the requirements of the production of products on the basis of consumption raqobatbardoshinnovatsion requires. Technical update and modernization of the main sectors of the economy in the country, the introduction of modern technology, providing innovative and competitive in the world market in order to encourage innovative projects in recent years, the program developed on the basis of a great work is being carried out.

“Today, many developed countries with leading positions in the world economy and bermoqdaki indisputable proven experience, and achieve raqobatbardrshlikka to world markets, primarily consistent reforms of the economy, from the aspect of structural change and diversification to enhance high-technologygreenhouses and new enterprises , production networks, the rapid developmentanish provide the operating capacities of modernization and technical at the expense of the speed of the update process can be done,”[1]

The main part.

Financing of innovative activity in a market economy is one of the important events of public investment, and ensures implementation of the following strategic objectives:

- science-advanced technique in practice through the implementation of technological achievement of the national economy rebuild from structural aspects to ensure;
- the priority direction of preservation and innovation science and technical potential of the country's economy development.

The world practice shows, only in the global economic competition fantexnika to create favorable conditions to the development of the business entity operating in a given country will have a relative advantage. In the opinion of experts, teachers makrotexnologiyaning 45 50 countries of the developed world has 80-90% in the export of high technology products these products are produced and developed countries to contribute to almost all had received.[2]

Organization of innovation the essence of the implementation of the development strategy adopted in order to make the function ik rejaviy established includes tasks to solve. This set of resources you want to do, the size of distribution issues, executive time setting, detection of cooperation of the participants, and do other work, you will need to provide control. (1-picture). The activities of leaders at all levels of management who has played a significant part of that innovation is one of the main functions of the organization. Innovation management in the organization of all elements of the innovation process effectively in order to complete rejaviy adopted the decision on the target volume according to time and space it provides, due to organizational decisions are important signs of germination up to tizimlashti turlanib and functions, forms and methods of understanding.

Innovation management innovation in the organization of various forms of use. The structure of the form of innovation in terms of content consists of various methods to carry out innovative projects of the division of labour. Such forms of

innovation to the organization in the concentration, and the specialized kooperatsiyalanish kombinatsiyalanishlarni you can add.

Picture 1. - Innovative form of organization[3]

The concentration of innovation in large firms increasingly in a certain direction, this means the process to a larger scale these up to. The process of expansion of innovation activity of small innovative business konsentratsiyalanishga the same ambitions as innovative as the most advanced areas of business funds to make natural market is one of the factors. As the form of organization of specialized innovation innovation and organizational structures in the construction of lk and limited to its appearance and the ways the type of work is known to be small and helping them attached to products used. The width of this innovative view of the innovation process within the framework of the development of these specialized ministry on the basis of rates and solid can be varied. Experience the modern organization in the world as an important form of kooperatsiyalash terms of innovative development of projects recognized. IK Kooperatsiyalash the difficulty of the implementation of projects and specialized, inter-organization cooperation for

the enhancement of innovation in the sphere of international koordinatsiya the development of full-scale production as the result of marketing research is the implementation of the program. The results already obtained in the organization of innovation in lk or combined raw materials, secondary materials and innovative production processes and is based on the use of encrgiya in the organization and implementation is manifested. Additional studies within the framework of effective firms bazaviy additional knowledge to get the effect, giving them a new area is introduced. The organizational forms of the organization of innovation processes listed above, the main weapon in the preparation of the decision. Boise formal and informal appearance they might have. The development of innovation activity in enterprises not only in the creation of the technical indicators of product innovation, but also costs related to the proper management of this innovative project. New products adapted to changing external and internal concentration is currently increasing the competitiveness of enterprises innovative projects in the market method and choose the right fit for the accounting of the costs of particular importance. Truth or implementation that lead to innovative projects in the innovative with the ultimate goal of all scientific, technological, organizational, financial, commercial, marketing're trying. Development and implementation of innovative projects which cover all economic activities depends on several surface phase korxo the process is carried out. Each stage of this process and will not be accomplished without the expense of a certain funds. Because these expenses in the account sufficient to lead on different costs and complex ko'pqirrali the reporting period, the shape and the place of formation and the different funding sources may be different.

Account management of innovative projects — this innovative project costs for management decisions in the short and long-term business enterprise planning, management, control, and data analysis on the results of innovation activities of the complex system. Today, economic entities, which would have made the

implementation of innovative projects, we have a "target on your work" (target costs), please use the system. This is because consumers in the system into account the requirements of new useful features at a predetermined value added products to create. "Target on your work" system — management system that so yes, the market due to its innovative new products to help reduce costs and without the relationship with planning, cost control is carried out in the targeted kalkulyasiya and costs. "Targetkosting" the system targeted the main indicators of the price, costs and targeted targeted benefits. "Target on your work" — based system so that to reduce these costs, usually targeted to the costs of the product is in demand in the market suitable kalkulyasiya. Since many years in developed countries "target on your work" in the production system, mainly used in the product being manufactured and the model of a new type of innovative projects is coming to life. Also, the "target on your work" system in the service sector, as well as working to damage launched on the activity of enterprises is also used.

Simple in the traditional system, the price is determined as follows:

$$\text{The Prime Cost} + \text{Profit} = \text{Price}$$

"Target on your work" in the system, while in the reverse direction will become here:

$$\text{Targeted Cost} - \text{Target Profit} = \text{Target Cost}$$

"Target on your work" in the system from another system, unlike the sales price to determine the sign of the costs are starting to provide. This sale price is determined through strong marketing surveys. To determine the expected costs from the purchase price of the targeted profit is lost. Then in the production process balmof all its participants nini managerto draw simple rda working to achieve target costs ko'zlanayotgan deals with the design of the product. Therefore, the "target on your work" the difference from the other system and the positive sides of the system as follows:

- product loyihalashtirilayotgan of the costs of each element

inobat takes two ikirchikirigacha;

- objects, to try to achieve targeted costs for different managers or non-standard is found, and this will lead to innovation;

- to achieve targeted costs and constant costs in comparison to the work of irresponsible excess prevents the mind to work with.

So, along with a "target on your work" system, there are cons:

- a new product , creating the process of a lot of and re-re - going to be lengthened as a result of design can be.

- "target on your work" way to put mistakes in the application of the system to working pressure to be overly that can have a negative impact;

- loyihalashtiruvchilar service and marketing costs for different kelishmovchiklar to achieve trust between staff in determining the price may come out.

Targeted sales price of new products , determining should perform the following:

- prospective analysis of market segments sales;
- new products to market requirements analysis; - analysis of the period hayotiylik new products.

The basis of the costs of innovative products targeted in opinion, you should perform the following:

- decisions based on the formation of costs analysis skills;
- the costs of innovative products targeted at the computer's analysis kalkulyasiya

to;

- analysis of business risks.

The policy, which came out, it is possible to conclude that a new product to the production of gone belgilamasdan expenses on the basis of price, innovative project management and make up on account of the "target on your work" the system

through the selection of targeted and targeted price the benefits of trade and economic conditions in the enterprises competitiveness, increase

motivation and paper products will increase. The method of evaluation points follows. The most important results of the project affecting omiarms is selected. Me'zon on the level of priority of dialing out. This can be detected from management, that is, to divide the group consists of a handle section and me'zon 100 of them are invited. Each me'zon mentioned on quality. The quantitative evaluation of the expression. They can identify with the way it professionals ifodalsh quantitative criteria (table 1).

Methodical recommendations on the evaluation and funding of innovative projects to choose them for state property committee of uzbekistan, the ministry of finance and the ministry of innovative project maqroiqtisodiyot tif approved by the agency following the main section of the efficiency defined:

- commercial (financial efficiency) financial impacts it directly to the participants is provided for the implementation of the project.
- done to increase the effectiveness of the project budget for the budget reflects the effects of regional and local state;
- economic efficiency of national economy innovation project that they can direct financial interest of the participants and measure evaluation within the framework of the implementation costs associated with the project and the results is provided.

The main methods to select innovative projects.[4]

The method name and a brief description	of the method the advantages	of the method are the disadvantages	of the method application environment
the disko method– cover your own self. Income cash flow the flow of money to the resurrection to xara jat tenglab to identify innadi.	Cash flow from the concept of uses. Refinancing of money and the possibility of chalik may be time cost is taken into account.	You national currency convertible is ineffective unless it works.	Stable economic environment.
Net current value method. Income and expenses are defined as the difference between the amount of net cash flow or from a project. If you kursatgich is greater than 0, 0 if the project will take , is equal to this project directory uninterested	the stockholders of thisr the benefits of the increase was aimed.	Sometimes a large expenditure is required. The project is long - term bit directory when the number will come directly.	Profitable enterprises and different cash flow , which is able to project muhitda.

The commercial effectiveness of the project (financial basis) required is determined by the norms of providing income and the financial costs of an effective relationship.

For commercial projects as investments on account of the effectiveness of individual participants with their rules for the scan can be considered. For this step in smart serves as the flow of real money.

Conclusion. The results of the effectiveness of the implementation of the project appropriate section of the budget (federal, regional, local) reflects the impact of the budget revenues and costs. The project implied in regional and federal support chormany years ago the purpose of the user base is a result of effective budget the main section of the budget.

The effect of integrated or integrated effect as the sum of discounted annual budget budget budget budget costs can be considered as the integrated increase of income.

World experience in research, scientific-technical and business at the same time there is a difference between the experimental discovery. News of the market of intellectual labor representatives to be scientists, engineers and other experts as a result of the work occurs. How effective are the results of their labor, even so high that is. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added. The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.

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